
COUNCIL ON
LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.
THIRTY-SECOND
ANNUAL REPORT/1988

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ANNUAL REPORT/1988

1785 Massachusetts Ave., N.W.
Washington, D.C. 20036

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The scholar at his book-wheel is a reproduction of an engraving in Agostino Ramelli's *Le diverse et artificiose machine* . . . Paris, 1588. It first appeared in the Council's third annual report, with the following explanation: "the picture symbolizes the interest of the Council on Library Resources in both the content of books and the mechanics of library service." The engraving has appeared in each annual report since that time.

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2. Beginning August 1987.
 3. Beginning February 1988.
 4. Resigned, June 1988.
 5. Resigned, January 1988.

Foreword

John E. Sawyer retired this year as president of The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation and we want to acknowledge here the assistance he and the Mellon Foundation have given to libraries. CLR is especially indebted to Jack Sawyer for his wise advice and consistent support. When The Ford Foundation—after twenty years as the sole source of CLR funds—reduced its role, Jack Sawyer took the lead and enlisted the interest of several private foundations in the work of the Council. He acted with dispatch because he was convinced that the connection between educational distinction and library performance was real and important. Mellon leadership not only kept CLR alive and well but also stimulated effective collaboration among research libraries, promoted automation activities, and pressed the cause of preservation on every front. In fact, the preservation movement that at long last seems about to flourish owes more than anyone knows to Jack Sawyer's perception and persistence.

Private foundation funding for independent and academic research libraries has increased substantially during the past fifteen years, and it is no accident that that change coincided with Jack Sawyer's tenure as Mellon president. He saw scholarly communication as a whole; he recognized early on that the scholarly disciplines, scholarly publishing, and research libraries were inseparable enterprises, and he acted time and again on that belief.

As the library world's operating foundation, CLR has been fortunate to have had the enthusiastic support of Jack Sawyer. And, as one who had his term as CLR president coincide with Jack Sawyer's presence at Mellon, I am grateful for thoughtful guidance and subtle help of many kinds. Reflecting on the methods of a foundation president, Jack once noted that it is all well and good to look at the stable as a whole when considering a case, but in the end you have to look in the stall. Both CLR and its president are pleased to have passed his test.

Warren J. Haas

PROGRAM REVIEW

The Fourth Decade

One of the most important undertakings of 1987/88 was to review the CLR program and to establish Council direction for the next few years. Informal meetings with many individuals and subsequent CLR Board discussions have resulted in "The Fourth Decade." As this year ends, we are at work turning these objectives into action for 1988/89.

Over the years, the program of the Council on Library Resources has been consistent in intent but has periodically shifted in emphasis, reflecting changing needs and opportunities. The initial focus was on developing and applying various technologies and techniques to specific library operations. The general thrust of that effort gradually became concentrated on the application of computers to bibliographic processes, a primary element of the CLR program for nearly twenty years. Library management began to receive serious attention when universities and their libraries entered the period of growth that dominated the 1960s and much of the following decade and that made those institutions the costly and complex enterprises they are today. At the same time, the Council moved into the international world, recognizing that the work of libraries is not bounded by national borders. In 1969, CLR introduced what has become a diverse series of programs designed to help individual librarians develop new skills and engage in academic research. During the past decade, the importance of cooperative approaches to meeting widely shared operating responsibilities—bibliographic services and preservation are prime examples—has been reflected in CLR activities.

The Council's program has been a cumulative one, with new elements supplementing rather than replacing what has gone before. But, as the program has expanded in scope, limits on staff size and financial resources have forced concentration on specific targets of greatest importance. Stronger ties with key academic bodies have been developed because of the natural relationships between library performance and costs, on the one hand, and the interests and concerns of faculty and university officers on the other.

But present-day CLR characteristics have not stemmed solely from the Council's own evolution. The information world, taken as a whole, is far different from what it was in 1956, CLR's first year. A report prepared in

1981 by CLR Board members Ruth Davis and Robert Vosper and their colleagues on a Board Special Committee is a masterful description of the growing complexity of the library and information arena, and the Council's program and methods have been and continue to be greatly influenced by the suggestions incorporated in that report. The changes identified in 1981 have continued with full force. The sheer number of "information" organizations that have come into being and the span of interests they and their constituencies reflect have affected prospects for cohesion between libraries and related parts of the information world. In this wider context, CLR may be less visible than it once was, but the importance of what it seeks to do is not diminished and seems unlikely to be, so long as we persist in concentrating our efforts and resources on topics of fundamental importance. In a sense, it is because CLR does not have a fixed constituency that it has been able to maintain its position as an effective force in a time of growing competition.

While academic and research libraries have long been CLR's primary concern, much of what we have been doing affects libraries of many kinds. Further, the way the academic community puts information to use is a topic that is becoming inseparable from how society at large does so. And, while concentrating on currently important issues, the Council also tries to take the long view. As an integrating force, CLR remains for many an important component in the new information setting, as it has been for more than thirty years.

Given the validity of this conclusion about CLR itself, it is time once again to look ahead, to make certain that what we do will be useful in meeting anticipated needs and appropriate in the light of probable future conditions. For thirty years, the Council's program has rested on the bedrock of librarianship, so it is not likely that any amount of reflection will much change the basic thrust of our efforts. From the beginning, library management (both words expansively defined) and the professions that are most responsible for collecting and enabling the use of recorded information have been the keystones of the CLR agenda.

These two established elements, one focused on operations and the other on the education and capabilities of individuals, must clearly continue to receive full attention. But a third topic, as fundamental in its own way as the others, is slowly taking shape. There is a desperate need for a better definition and understanding of the new world of information, specifically as it will affect teaching and learning at all levels and in all settings and, more generally, as it will influence the public activities and private enterprises that are contiguous to education, scholarship, and research. With its carefully nurtured independence and its record of support for the organizations and individuals that have taken the lead in the "old" world of library and information services, CLR has much to contribute to the definition of the "new." Simply put, we need to make the search for ideas and ideals an integral part of our concern for organizations and individuals.

Unless agreement is reached on the principles that should shape our

information future, libraries of all types will be at risk, as will be the intellectual activity they support, nationally and internationally. CLR is not alone in bringing attention to the issues that are inherent in the application of information technology, but at this point, the CLR inclination to encourage inquiry, speculation, and cooperation is a useful asset in an arena where domination is too often the driving force.

The CLR Program

The accompanying chart describes CLR in broad outline. Most activities are incorporated in two primary programs that encompass all CLR-initiated projects and most externally generated proposals. While in recent years an increasing portion of CLR activity has been internally initiated, CLR continues to respond to inquiries and to review and consider for funding all proposals submitted, so long as they are pertinent to the Council's general objectives and do not seek support for purposes that are, for reasons of policy, excluded (e.g., operating funds, equipment, and facilities).

This report concentrates on the two primary programs, but for full reference to the chart the following points are noted:

1. The Commission on Preservation and Access, which was established by CLR, has incorporated as a separate nonprofit organization. Appropriate functional ties between CLR and the Commission will be maintained, and CLR will continue to provide support services.
2. As an operating foundation, CLR both manages programs and grants funds to others—institutions, organizations, and individuals. Occasionally, CLR will enter into a contract for a specified study or other work. Grants are awarded and contracts are made in response to proposals submitted to CLR, either unsolicited or in response to invitations growing out of a CLR-managed program. All proposals for grants are processed uniformly in that there is an internal review process, an external review when there is a need for additional expert advice, and some form of team review for competitive programs. The CLR Board considers and acts on grant applications passing staff review.

Several general observations are appropriate before moving on to program descriptions. First, it should be emphasized that CLR defines the words libraries and librarians broadly. Our starting point is libraries, but all organizations concerned with gathering and providing access to the "written" record are, from most points of view, inseparable enterprises. That fact needs to be acknowledged in all that we seek to do. By the same token, librarians, while the most visible of the professions involved in assuring continuity of the record, have many counterparts. In short, the arena is a broad one and responsibility is diffused.

Council on Library Resources
Operating and Program Organization

Second, libraries, archives, and other repositories historically have concentrated on building collections where growth and permanence are assumed. This obligation continues, but another responsibility, born of new technological capabilities, must also be met: that is, to supply information in smaller and more precise segments, more rapidly and from a growing number of sources. Libraries are addressing the new challenge with the same skill and tenacity they have employed in meeting the traditional demands of their profession. The substance of libraries has not fundamentally changed, but the range of the services they provide has.

Finally, the scope of the Council's own interests is being reconsidered. As an unendowed operating foundation that is dependent on private foundations for funding, CLR has always faced constraints; even so, CLR recognizes a need to address additional concerns. From the beginning, while "libraries and archives" were the Council's theoretical domain, the focus was on academic and research libraries. The chain of intellectual communication, while increasingly compartmentalized by subject, is now less so in terms of process. The development of technology-based information services offers the prospect of improved access to many kinds of information for individuals outside the organized academic and research communities. Public libraries, especially, may have a much-expanded role to play. Recognizing this fact, CLR will, as appropriate and possible, look for ways to be useful to those public librarians who will help shape the future of these important institutions.

By the same token, we need to pay even more attention than we have to international matters. The Council has strongly asserted the importance of equitable access to information. This is a principle that cannot be subject to chance affiliations or constrained by national borders. As we are able to do so, these important considerations will find their way into the Council's programs.

Program I. Library Management and Operations

The future library is the dominant subject for CLR attention. Through research, experiment, demonstration, and communication, we will do what we can to help librarians and users of libraries shape the form of that future.

For thirty years, the internal operations and general management of academic and research libraries have been primary CLR targets. Much staff effort and most CLR funds have been used to explore new organizational and staffing structures for libraries, to help librarians acquire new management skills, and to promote improved efficiency in many facets of library operations. In order to increase the number of options available to libraries, CLR has assisted in the development of integrated computerized bibliographic services, a national preservation program, and cooperative cataloging. This attention to effective administration has helped librarians to build and operate the expanded library systems that are now required to support research and scholarship.

But despite past success and continuing effort, there is growing concern

among librarians, university officers, and many library users about what the future holds. The demand for services and resources grows constantly, but serious questions are now being raised about projected costs, about the pattern of current expenditures, about the influence of technology, and about the effectiveness of existing administrative structures for providing library and information services. In light of these concerns, many librarians are now having trouble defining their plans for the future and turning those plans into a course of action that is understood, endorsed, and funded. Compounding the difficulty, many academic institutions are themselves often unable to look beyond the next fiscal year, much less five or ten.

Simply because first-rate libraries are required if scholarship and research are to flourish, CLR must continue work in this arena. But given the extent and significance of present concerns, it also seems essential that we accelerate and expand our efforts to concentrate on what libraries must become at some future time if they are to remain effective, even indispensable, components of academic and scholarly enterprises and of society itself.

The Council's research program, now in its third year, marked the beginning of this new concentration. Most projects funded have been case studies—not so much of the future form of libraries but of possible ways to address the question of how plans for the future might be made and used. It is evident from the work done to date that planning for libraries is difficult and time consuming. It is obvious as well that planning must be a collaborative effort. There are also limits to what can be planned; a capacity to accommodate the future is as important as planning for it. But despite these and many other lessons learned, we are firmly convinced that the effort to redefine the form of library and information services must continue because the risks of not doing so are too great. Put simply, libraries, universities, the academic disciplines, and the interested public must join forces to set their specifications for the future and to devise responsible ways for meeting them.

Reflecting this conviction, the research program entered a new stage early in 1988 with the formation of the Research Library Committee by CLR, in partnership with the American Council of Learned Societies, the Social Science Research Council, and the Association of American Universities. Members of the new committee include university presidents and provosts, faculty members from the humanities and social sciences, librarians, and archivists.

It is this Committee that will provide future guidance to the Council and its research program. Two organizational meetings have served to identify an initial agenda and to establish a way of proceeding. It is the Committee's intent to concentrate on issues and problems that are important and tractable, and that offer the prospect that work devoted to them will be influential. Examples of topics that are being considered for attention will give an indication of the Committee's interests:

- The process of establishing policy for library and information services in research universities.
- The relationships between library functions and practices, on the one

hand, and the needs and styles of use of individuals and disciplines on the other.

- Legal rights and constraints affecting the application of information technologies, consortial activities, preservation, and public policy.
- The costs and funding of “public good” undertakings.
- The effect of publishing practices on scholarship and library operations.
- The kinds and quality of services to scholarship provided by the Library of Congress and other national agencies.
- Alternative future forms for research libraries and implications of each for costs, funding, performance, and institutional organization.

Concentrated study by the Research Library Committee and its subcommittees and by consultants, staff, and grantees on chosen topics; subsequent consideration of results; and recommendations for action by the Committee, which includes distinguished individuals from the pertinent components of the academic world, should help improve understanding of the issues and promote broadly based support for specific courses of action. If library collections, professional skills, and operating capabilities are to be effectively used, exceptional effort will be required by all parties in order that (1) members of faculties and university administrations might understand the underlying reasons for the directions being taken by libraries, (2) librarians might address productively the specific interests and concerns of faculty and meet the expectations of university officers, and (3) national programs and extensive cooperative activities might be critically assessed in the context of user needs, technological capabilities, and funding requirements.

While the work of the Research Library Committee is at the heart of Program I, the Council will continue to establish and maintain a limited number of specialized and important undertakings. Ongoing support for such entities as the Network Advisory Committee, the Linked Systems Project Policy Committee, and the Commission on Preservation and Access are examples of CLR ties to external groups. The Bibliographic Services Study Committee is an example of a CLR-based operation. Careful attention will be given to maintaining the flow of information between these specialized enterprises and Research Library Committee members.

The structure for Program I is flexible and the agenda is—and will become even more—complex, but there is no other way to proceed that is both collaborative and adventuresome. The CLR role is not to prescribe the future but to expedite the search.

Program II. Librarianship and Professional Education

If the redefinition of libraries is the task at hand, then a new and accurate understanding of the substance of librarianship and the bolstering of professional skills are parallel and essential requirements for success. In the end, it is the intent and abilities of individuals that will determine the nature and performance of the future library.

A review of the CLR programs that have supported research by librarians, provided opportunities for continuing development, and encouraged improvement in basic professional education has been completed recently. While the value of these programs for many individual librarians has been great, the influence of CLR efforts on professional education has been subtle at best—in part, perhaps, because the scale of the Council's involvement has been insufficient.

More is required: more support in more ways for individuals and more effort and imagination on behalf of professional education. The reasons are clear. First, the difficult transition of libraries from the present to the future must, in large part, be accomplished by those who are now librarians, working with others in allied fields. The work will require new skills, new insights, new methods, and new affiliations. The most productive, energetic, and imaginative individuals—acknowledged and potential leaders—must be given every possible advantage to assure their success. Second, professional education, with its mix of strengths and problems, is not yet up to the task of fueling the future with the women and men of the quality required to do the job. In terms of the CLR role, we can find ways to help many more individuals because we have shown we are able to do so. And, even though the way is not yet certain, our advisors, both librarians and educators, assert that CLR must assume at least some of the responsibility for promoting, through academic means, the cause and substance of the profession itself.

The starting point for work on both aspects of Program II is our understanding of issues, concerns, and problems that have been identified in a series of formal and informal CLR-sponsored meetings in recent years. We have now consolidated all educational activities into a cohesive program and are at work establishing the resources and structure that will enable CLR to make a long-term commitment to librarians and librarianship.

Continuing Education and Professional Research

While final decisions have yet to be made, plans to expand support for individuals are well advanced. Several established programs will be continued, although perhaps with modifications. These include (1) the Cooperative Research Program, which is primarily intended to stimulate interest in and to develop skills for structured research on topics pertinent to library operations and services; (2) the Academic Library Management Intern Program; and (3) opportunities for intensive study by groups of individuals, exemplified by the UCLA Senior Fellows program and the Recent Graduates intern program.

Several additional programs, all in support of continuing education, are actively being explored, including (1) academic programs on topics such as long-range planning for key groups of specialized professional staff (e.g., subject specialists, archivists, and systems analysts); (2) a fellowship program and seminar series on the international aspects of library operations; and (3) a program, yet to be defined, to encourage public library leaders to explore

collaboratively the policy issues and public interests that affect public library performance.

Participation in continuing education programs is competitive and usually involves some level of personal or institutional cost sharing. These specifications are intended to focus funds on those who are identified by peers as present or potential leaders and to press libraries and their parent institutions to institutionalize and increase support for staff development opportunities during this critical period of transition.

Funding individuals to undertake academic research and professional projects is an important parallel to continuing education for any dynamic field. CLR has always entertained proposals for such work and, over the years, much of exceptional merit has been accomplished by many CLR grantees. But the research tradition in this discipline is not as broadly based as it must become and, in part for reasons of quality and content, not as influential as it should be. The Council will find ways to stimulate research activity, both by making this aspect of our program more widely known among librarians and those in allied fields and by promoting library-managed research on topics of substantial importance and promise, involving both library staff and other members of the university community.

Finally, the matter of recruiting exceptionally talented and well-prepared individuals to the profession needs attention. The key seems to be direct action by individual libraries and librarians, but CLR may have a useful support role to play.

Professional Education

If, in the near term, we are dependent on present library leadership, the performance of libraries in the early twenty-first century increasingly will be in the hands of those who have yet to begin their professional education. The present content and quality of that education have undergone much recent scrutiny and often severe criticism. Details are to be found in many places and need not be repeated here. In hopes of improving the situation, CLR has provided limited financial help to some library schools to encourage experiment and constructive change, but results have been disappointing when measured against need. With this experience and after many constructive discussions, we have concluded that, while a few schools may flourish and stand out from the pack, there is still no ideal model for professional education. The great majority of library schools seem unlikely to develop the capabilities and vitality that a hard-pressed profession desperately needs. Because academic enterprises shape their own destinies, direct action by CLR is neither appropriate nor possible, but it is still essential that the Council find a way to be useful. Improvement will come only if the intellectual foundation for professional education is enriched, admission requirements are raised, pertinent academic subjects are adequately represented, and faculties are of sufficient size and distinction to assure visibility and credibility for library schools within the universities of which they are a part. If CLR cannot

directly influence the schools, perhaps it can work indirectly by helping to address these matters. It is not yet clear how this might best be done, but it is obvious that we need to build on what strength there is. This is an undertaking in which the difficulty is a good match for the importance.

At heart, the objective is to define and give visibility to the discipline of information studies and to enlist in the work of that discipline individuals from a number of fields. Information studies is concerned with questions related to the organization of knowledge; information use and needs; institutional and public policies; the processes by which information is assembled, organized, and distributed; and the structure and performance of the organizations and institutions (universities themselves as well as libraries) that are centrally involved. It is our conviction that the profession of librarianship needs to be redefined but that a new definition will come only when the academic foundation for professional education is itself clarified and unified. Understanding the substance of information studies is a prelude to mastering the skills needed to operate and manage libraries.

If CLR is to move ahead, there are many requirements. A program committee will be formed to assist with program development and to provide ongoing assistance. Membership will include informed and forward-looking individuals from all of the components of librarianship and related professions and from university administration and pertinent academic disciplines. Since success in improving professional education hinges on expanding and strengthening research capabilities and making research results more influential, research itself will get strong and continuing attention. Help will be required from universities willing to explore prospects and individual faculty members within those institutions willing to take the lead. Many approaches will need to be considered and tried, including, perhaps, the creation of one or more centers of information studies, development of a specialized fellowship program, organization of seminars, a publications program, and experimental courses in information studies for doctoral students in other disciplines. At least five years of hard work will be required for experiment and installation of new educational components, but at the end of that time the influence of that work should begin to be felt.

CLR can help by encouraging production of a summary of what has been learned thus far about the way the world of information works and by promoting a new educational agenda for a profession that must grow in substance and in influence. This is the task that should highlight CLR's fourth decade.

Research

The Council's research program has three distinct but related foci. **Institutional grants** are made for the purpose of stimulating and encouraging collaborative projects among various units of the university—departments, schools, institutes—and the university library. **Individual grants** are made in response to research proposed by a single scholar or a small number of collaborators who may or may not have a specific functional connection to the university library. Thirdly, a newly formed Research Library Committee is charting a plan that will result in **commissioned studies** of the future of academic information services.

Institutional Grants

The Council's first institutional grant was made to the University of California, Los Angeles, in 1985. The overall objective was to stimulate strategic planning for future information services required by the several schools and departments of the university. Under the coordinating leadership of the Dean of the Graduate School of Library and Information Science, some eighteen different planning initiatives have been undertaken to inquire into a broad range of information issues. Separate departmental initiatives have stimulated much additional activity. Most recently, strategic planning for information resources and services has been added to the university-wide effort at UCLA to develop an Academic Strategic Plan, under the direction of a vice-chancellor.

Smaller in size and more narrowly focused than the UCLA activity is a 1987 grant to the University of Minnesota to support a collaboration among the University Libraries, the Hubert H. Humphrey Institute of Public Affairs, and the Curtis L. Carlson School of Management. The objective is to develop an "integrated information center" to serve the needs of faculty and graduate students of the Humphrey Institute. A successful center could serve as a model for future specialized information services of all sorts and might be emulated elsewhere in the University of Minnesota as well as in other academic research environments. The Minnesota group began with an assessment of the information requirements of the Humphrey Institute scholars and a forecast of the likely resources and services to be provided in the future by information technology. It is also evaluating alternative organizational struc-

tures for managing an integrated information center, and analyzing funding and recovery of costs. Policy and legal issues will also be addressed. The final phase of the project will be the development of a Model Information Center.

An institutional grant to Carnegie Mellon University in 1987 supported a study group, involving the University Libraries, the Department of Computer Science, and the Laboratory for Computational Linguistics, which investigated problems in the structuring of electronic text. The thrust of this grant was to identify and explore the issues involved in making large amounts of text available for distribution through electronic media. Recognizing the diversity of interests involved in such issues, the study group conducted a conference for librarians, educators, publishers, investigators, and information vendors to discuss the aims, needs, and problems of electronic publication. The conference featured presentations and discussion of mark-up language, experience with full-text documents online, the possibilities of hypertext, problems of retrieval, copyright, and economic issues.

A fourth institutional grant, to the University of Illinois at Chicago, enabled two members of the university library staff to spend a year as participants at the University's Institute for the Humanities. The objective was to begin a process of engaging faculty in exploring, with the library, questions pertaining to the methods and informational tools they use to do their research, how they communicate their work, and how that work is disseminated. This process was to be the beginning of a larger effort to identify for the university as a whole the major issues of information policy, including the nature of users, the sources available to them (whether under university control or not), the locations of information resources, and their costs. In effect, this effort is pointed toward the development of a university plan for dealing with these issues. The Illinois grant will culminate in a national conference on information resources in the humanities, scheduled for spring 1989.

Individual Grants

Elizabeth Liddy and Robert Oddy of Syracuse University received Council support for research on two related topics: how to represent better the information content of documents, and how to assist users to better present their needs to an information system. They began with the assumption that a user's ordinary query may not be a suitable representation of the information the system is prepared to provide—e.g., the user may ask for information on "encouraging work habits" while the article that would provide it might be entitled "Incentives to Increase Labor Force Participation." The research is directed toward determining the linguistic structure of users' problem statements and the features that could be used in a computer program for identifying the discourse-level components of problem statements. An accompanying task—determining the structure of the retrievable text—is to be accomplished by analyzing the structure of abstracts of scientific articles. Ultimately, the research is directed toward designing an automated information

retrieval system that can negotiate between the content of the literature and the content of the user's inquiry.

At the University of Missouri-Columbia, MaryEllen Sievert, an assistant professor of information science, and Donald Sievert, a professor of philosophy, have begun a study of the information requirements of philosophy faculty and graduate students at a number of universities in the Midwest. The research will focus on four questions: What materials do philosophers use and how do they go about finding these materials? If, as is suspected, philosophers tend to use only a few secondary sources, what are they missing and what is the importance of these omissions for their teaching and research? In what ways are philosophy faculty and graduate students likely to use new indices and other sources of information as they become available? And, what do philosophers expect in the way of library resources and services? The investigators will approach these questions in two ways: first, philosophy faculty currently engaged in research will be offered free online searches of their research topics in exchange for their evaluation of usefulness or relevance of each citation retrieval—thereby establishing an estimate of how much significant material may be being missed by ignoring bibliographic databases. Second, a survey of faculty and graduate students in philosophy will inquire into patterns of use of libraries and their services at Big Ten and Big Eight universities, and will probe the needs and preferences of respondents for modes of acquiring information.

Research Library Committee

Early in 1988, the Council organized a Research Library Committee with the active collaboration of the American Council of Learned Societies, the Association of American Universities, and the Social Science Research Council. (Members of the Committee are listed on page 46.) Composed of more than two dozen individuals—university presidents, provosts, deans, librarians, scholars from several fields, foundation officers, and information scientists—the Committee's purpose is to plan and oversee the execution of a schedule of investigations, studies, and probing position papers whose end is the specifications for the research library of the future. The Committee's topical agenda is tentatively set to include: the governance of libraries, legal rights and constraints affecting information flow, the effects of publishing practices on libraries and scholarship, national and international information services to scholarship, the relationships between library functions and scholarly or disciplinary styles of work, and the bibliographic situation of the humanities.

It is the Council's hope that this collaborative undertaking will make possible realistic planning for the research library of the future that takes into account the needs and constraints of all the parties who must participate in that planning. If the research library of the future is to flourish and meet the needs of its supporters and patrons, it is necessary that faculty and administration understand the underlying forces at work on libraries; that librarians

address productively the concerns of faculty and the expectations of administration; and that everyone's vision be broadened to a critical appreciation of the possibilities inherent in national programs and cooperative activities in the light of future user needs, technological capabilities, and funding requirements. All of these aspects require an investment in analytical studies and research.

Research Program Projects Active in 1987/1988

Association of Research Libraries

To help defray the expenses of a three-day planning retreat for the Association's leadership.

Carnegie Mellon University

To establish a study group to examine the purpose and uses of electronic text in education and research, and to discuss production and distribution of electronic text.

European Foundation for Library Cooperation

To stimulate cooperative research and development in European librarianship.

State University of New York, Albany

To publish the proceedings of an international conference on classification in the computer age.

Abigail Dahl-Hansen Studdiford

To identify public policy issues that affect major United States research libraries and the effect of these issues on federal funding for research libraries.

Syracuse University

To study the structure of problem statements and abstracts as a basis for improving information retrieval system design.

University of California, Los Angeles

To develop a university-based research program focused on the issues, problems, and needs for research with respect to long-range strategic planning for libraries and information resources in the research university of the future.

University of California, Los Angeles

To conduct a conference involving Senior Fellows and members of the Research Library Committee in consideration of the research library of the future, to be held in August 1988.

University of California, Los Angeles

To assemble a low-cost, microcomputer-based digital imaging system as a tool for the preservation of library materials.

University of Illinois at Chicago

To engage fellows and scholars at the Institute for the Humanities at UIC in examining topics related to strategic planning issues for the research university.

University of Minnesota

To develop a model academic information center as part of the Hubert H. Humphrey Institute of Public Affairs Library.

University of Missouri-Columbia

To investigate the information-seeking behavior and information requirements of philosophers.

Program Meetings, 1987/1988**Research Library Committee**

January 18, 1988 (New York City)

May 12, 1988 (Washington, D.C.)

Research Library Committee Subcommittee on Copyright

May 17, 1988 (Princeton, New Jersey)

Access to Information

The Access to Information program has been funded for the past five years by a grant from The Ford Foundation. The Council has initiated activities and awarded grants to libraries and individuals to promote equitable access to information and to study all aspects of information delivery systems that provide the resources needed by library users.

Grants in the Access program have taken many forms, but the most numerous awards have been cooperative research grants (see page 35 for a complete list). Working collaboratively, librarians and teaching faculty have identified practical research projects designed to help solve some of the access problems of libraries. In 1987/88, CLR grantees have produced guides to previously unavailable resources, conducted experiments to improve and facilitate online catalog access, and studied the information-seeking behaviors of several disciplinary groups. Many of the cooperative research grants have explored the application of technology to improve access to library materials.

In the interest of increasing access to Japanese scientific and technical information, a grant was made to the British Library for an international conference on the subject. As a result of the grant, the proceedings of the conference will be available to U.S. libraries at reduced cost.

CLR staff met with directors of sixty-two liberal arts colleges at Grinnell College (Iowa) in October 1987. A number of Council programs were discussed, but access to research resources and machine-readable data for collegiate institutions was identified as especially important.

Lawrence Dowler, archivist at the Harvard University Library, has begun a study of how scholars use archives and what their research needs are likely to be in the future. The first phase of the project involves consultations with archivists from other universities and non-university repositories to help him in framing the larger inquiry and developing a methodology for it. Following that interaction and extensive discussions with scholars using various Harvard archives, Dowler will plan a national study of collection use, research needs, and archival practice. CLR funded a planning meeting for the project.

Access Projects Active in 1987/1988

American Antiquarian Society

To assist in completing a machine-readable catalog of materials printed before 1801 in the United States and Canada, and to integrate the records with those in the Eighteenth-Century Short Title Catalogue.

American Historical Association

To conduct a planning meeting for a new *Guide to Historical Literature*.

American Nurses' Foundation, Inc.

To locate historical nursing materials held in archives, libraries, and historical societies and to compile a guide to their locations.

Trudi Bellardo, The Catholic University of America

To complete a history of the development of online information retrieval systems.

Mary Biggs, Columbia University

To conduct a survey of the six hundred faculty of ALA-accredited library schools to determine how they regard and use the research literature of their field.

The British Library

To publish the proceedings of the International Conference on Japanese Scientific and Technical Information.

Columbia University

To determine the overlap between the *Avery Index to Architectural Periodicals* and the *Architectural Periodicals Index*.

Enoch Pratt Free Library

To provide partial funding for the Enoch Pratt Free Library Centennial Symposium on metropolitan libraries facing the future.

Holy Family College

To test a previously developed prototype method of analyzing syllabi as a way to encourage faculty participation in collection development.

The Library of Congress

To support partially a conference on libraries and scholarly communication in the United States.

Louisiana State University

To demonstrate the use of a shelflist sample methodology to illustrate similarities and differences among library collections and to postulate the use of such profiles as a basis for cooperative collection development.

Louisiana State University

To explore methods of recognizing depreciation of library collections.

National Information Standards Organization

Travel support for a U.S. representative to advance an international standard for permanent paper.

North Texas State University

To test the use of cognitive styles inventories to predict the success of online database searchers.

Ohio State University

To develop a formula for cost effectiveness for use with a previously developed reference service model.

Pennsylvania State University

To enable Charles Townley to prepare a manuscript for library practitioners on developing library consortial relationships.

Pennsylvania State University

To assess the library and information needs of the Speech Communication Department.

The Research Libraries Group, Inc.

For partial costs of travel for Library of Congress personnel attending RLG Archives, Manuscripts and Special Collections Task Force meetings.

The Research Libraries Group, Inc.

To analyze the RLG Conspectus as a collection management tool.

The Research Libraries Group, Inc.

To coordinate a project to create a national database of descriptions of state government records within the Research Libraries Information Network.

University of Hawaii at Manoa

To study library users and uses of full-text databases.

University of Kentucky

To enable Lois M. Chan to compile a bibliographic guide to indexing languages used in online bibliographic databases.

University of Maryland

To compare two microcomputer-based systems for use by teachers in evaluating potential curricular materials.

University of Michigan

To support partially a second European Conference on Archives, to be hosted by the University of Michigan.

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

To study the U.S. regional depository libraries to establish baseline data and to determine the relationship of these libraries to one another and to the library community.

University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

To examine the relationship between subjects requested by users of an online catalog and the actual circulation of materials during a given period.

University of Western Ontario

To conduct two experiments to investigate the contributions of text superstructures and bibliographic structures that may affect the user-intermediary interaction of information systems.

University of Wisconsin

To examine, by mail questionnaire and focus-group interviews, the information-seeking behavior and information needs of research scholars in the field of women's studies.

Program Meetings, 1987/1988

Planning meeting for a seminar on researchers' use of archives
May 21, 1988 (Cambridge, Massachusetts)

Bibliographic Services

Bibliographic structures are at the core of virtually all library resource-sharing programs and access systems. Substantial CLR resources have been invested over the years in a bibliographic system configuration that will allow library patrons at any location to have complete access to bibliographic information, no matter what its source.

The plan for a virtual national bibliographic structure was implemented through projects funded by the Bibliographic Service Development Program. Now that the formal program has ended, two coordinating committees are overseeing the work required to install the Linked Systems Protocols that ultimately will allow the exchange of bibliographic records from one network to another.

The Linked Systems Project is coordinated by the Policy and Technical committees. (Members of the committees are listed on page 44.) In 1987/88, the LSP Policy Committee met once, giving special attention to the question of migration of LSP protocols to OSI (Open Standard Interconnection) standards and the requirements for exchange of bibliographic records. The LSP Technical Committee, managed by the Library of Congress and chaired by David Bishop, met twice to work out the details required at the systems level to implement the OSI standards and to schedule the migration in stages.

The Bibliographic Analysis group, a subcommittee of the Linked Systems Project, met on September 21–22, 1987, at the Library of Congress to review standards for exchanging bibliographic records via the linked system. After appropriate background work and review by a number of LSP participants, the standards for bibliographic records were accepted in November 1987.

The National Coordinated Cataloging Project moved into training and operational phases during the year. Eight research libraries agreed to contribute original cataloging records for certain categories of materials directly to the Library of Congress (LC) for immediate distribution via MARC (MACHINE-Readable Cataloging) tapes. The time between receipt of books and availability of cataloging records through network databases is expected to be reduced significantly, and the number of records for non-English language materials is expected to increase as a result of the cooperative project. During the year, equipment was installed in each of the participating libraries, and staff members were trained by LC staff in the specific requirements for national-level cataloging. Actual production of cataloging records that will be available to all libraries having access to MARC tapes will begin in 1988/89.

The Coordinated Cataloging Project is but a beginning in a long-term commitment to increase the quality and quantity of cataloging records available to libraries for use in processing local collections at reduced cost. To monitor the work of the Coordinated Cataloging Project and to ensure that managerial concerns are addressed, CLR appointed a Bibliographic Services Study Committee. Carol Mandel, Columbia University, was named chairperson; she was joined by Dorothy Gregor (University of California, San Diego) and Martin Runkle (University of Chicago). Paul Kantor (Tantalus Inc.) has been retained as a consultant to the Committee. The group met three times during the year to plan a study of ARL cataloging practices. ARL libraries will be surveyed in 1988 to determine the variations in practices between original and copy cataloging, and to predict the subsequent financial savings in copy cataloging. Methods and practices that seem to be cost effective will be reported for the benefit of other libraries.

In the longer term, the committee will study several aspects of equitable access to bibliographic information, including the need to enhance the bibliographic structure for humanistic scholarship. Questions arising from the Research Library Committee about the bibliographic system will be referred to this committee for study.

Karen Markey (University of Michigan) and Diane Vazine-Goetz (OCLC, Inc.) produced an interim report on their study of automated techniques for linking subject terms entered by users of online catalogs with the controlled vocabulary of the online catalog. An advisory committee consisting of Lois Chan (University of Kentucky), Pauline Cochrane (Catholic University), and Carolyn Frost (University of Michigan) will study the mid-project findings and will make recommendations for further analysis in the second phase of the project. A project review meeting will be held at the Library of Congress in September 1988.

CLR continued to fund the Network Advisory Committee's program planning efforts. The topics for 1987/88 were the role of networks and copyright.

Bibliographic Services Projects Active in 1987/1988

Columbia University

For a study to measure the impact of online public access catalog implementation on all aspects of public services at the Columbia University Libraries.

Linked Systems Project

Participants: The Library of Congress, the OCLC Online Computer Library Center, The Research Libraries Group, and the Western Library Network.

To design, develop, test, and implement a standardized telecommunications link, or Standard Network Interconnection, to permit exchange of data, initially among LC, OCLC, RLG, and WLN computer systems and, ultimately, between any two computer systems.

To implement the exchange of authority records, using the Standard Network Interconnection.

To analyze requirements and develop additional functional specifications for the online exchange of bibliographic records and related information, using communication links developed in the Linked Systems Project.

Northwestern University

To implement a standard network interconnection in NOTIS, a local library system.

OCLC Online Computer Library Center and The University of Michigan

To test and evaluate automated techniques to link subject terms entered by online catalog users with the library catalog's own controlled vocabulary.

Stanford University

To investigate end-user searching of bibliographic databases by comparing the effectiveness and costs of using DIALOG command language with the Institute for Scientific Information's Sci-Mate intermediary software.

University of California, Los Angeles

To conduct a workshop on the philosophical concepts underlying descriptive cataloging.

University of Illinois, Urbana-Champaign

To develop and evaluate online catalog interface enhancements that will provide expanded subject access to library collections through external databases.

Program Meetings, 1987/1988

Bibliographic Service Development Program Linked Systems Project

Policy Committee

September 3, 1987 (Washington, D.C.)

Technical Committee

October 29, 1987 (Washington, D.C.)

May 11, 1988 (Washington, D.C.)

Bibliographic Services Study Committee

December 10, 1987 (Washington, D.C.)

January 10, 1988 (San Antonio, Texas)

March 17, 1988 (Washington, D.C.)

Network Advisory Committee

October 28–30, 1987 (Washington, D.C.)

March 23–25, 1988 (Washington, D.C.)

Librarianship and Librarians

Basic professional education and continuing education for those already at work in libraries have been the subjects of much discussion within CLR during the year. As noted in the introduction to the annual report, a new and concentrated effort is planned in this area. The transformation of the research library cannot go forward without the concomitant enhancement of professional skills among those who must guide the transformation. Over the coming year, a professional education committee will give shape to the long-term program that is required.

During 1987/88, several grants made under the program entitled Internships for Recent Graduates were completed. The multi-institutional program in Chicago was conducted for a third and final year, and the University of Missouri-Columbia's two-year program was also completed. Thus far in this program, fifty-one relatively new librarians have been given the opportunity to learn more about the library in the context of the research university and about the library's contribution to the processes of research and teaching. Program activities at the University of Georgia will continue for another year, and planning is taking place for an internship program at Columbia University. Grant opportunities remain open to other libraries interested in establishing local internship programs.

Yale University, with a CLR grant, offered summer internships for three of its undergraduates in 1987 to introduce them to librarianship as a possible career. The results were encouraging, and a second grant was made to continue the program in the summer of 1988, increasing the number of internships to five.

Screening and selection for the Academic Library Management Intern Program took place in February and March of 1988. Three management interns were selected by the committee (members of the committee are listed on page 44): Patricia Iannuzzi of Yale University, to work with Joseph A. Rosenthal, director, University Library, University of California, Berkeley; Sarah Pritchard, Library of Congress, to work with Donald W. Koeppe, university librarian, Princeton University; and Sarah Watstein of Hunter College, to work with Norman D. Stevens, director of the University of Connecticut Library. The nine-month internships will begin on September 1, 1988. The three new interns bring the total number of individuals to participate in this program since its inception in 1974 to fifty.

The Association of Research Libraries' Office of Management Studies, with a grant to conduct a third Institute for Library Educators, solicited applications and selected twelve faculty members from U.S. and Canadian library schools to attend the two-week seminar on collection management, scheduled for August 1988 at the University of Chicago. The purpose of these institutes is to stimulate curriculum development that will introduce students to the complex issues of research librarianship.

Two cycles of cooperative research grants in 1987/88 resulted in funding for fifteen teams of researchers. These grants (listed separately on pages 35-39) continue to stimulate productive collaboration between practicing librarians and teaching faculty who have jointly identified library problems that can be addressed by a research project. The reports, generally of high quality, have been distributed widely through the professional literature and the ERIC Clearinghouse.

The Senior Fellows program at the University of California, Los Angeles, was funded to host a fifth class, scheduled for 1989. Publicity regarding the next Senior Fellows has been distributed and applications will be due by late fall, 1988.

The University of Chicago's Graduate Library School implemented its curriculum concentration in library automation and information systems with ongoing funding from the Council. During the academic year 1987/88, ten visiting speakers made presentations as part of the information systems lecture series; three visiting faculty were brought to the campus to teach specially designed courses; and eight master's degree students were supported by CLR Fellowships.

Professional Education Projects Active in 1987/88

Association of Research Libraries

To enable the Office of Management Studies to design, recruit for, and conduct a third Institute for Library Educators.

Columbia University

To plan a Library Fellows Program that will provide substantive orientation for librarians new to the profession and the research library environment.

Georgia State University

To conduct a study of occupational role identity and role image in four subspecialties of librarianship.

Indiana University

To commission three papers for a forum on research librarianship for Indiana University librarians and School of Library and Information Science faculty.

International Association of School Librarianship

Partial support for participants in the Seventeenth Annual Conference of the International Association of School Librarianship.

Louisiana State University

To implement a multidisciplinary curriculum for library systems analysts.

Simmons College

For a symposium on solutions to the problems of recruiting, educating, and training cataloging librarians.

University of California, Los Angeles

To continue the Senior Fellows program, which provides senior library administrators with opportunities for independent research and intensive, specialized study in management.

University of Chicago

For the third year of a multi-institutional internship program for recently hired library school graduates. Participating institutions are the University of Chicago Library and Graduate Library School, Northwestern University Libraries, and the University of Illinois at Chicago Library.

University of Chicago

To implement a special concentration in library automation and information systems and to stimulate awareness of the program within the university and library communities.

University of Georgia

To conduct an internship program to introduce recently hired library school graduates to the full range of issues important to the university and to librarianship generally.

University of Illinois, Urbana-Champaign

To study the perceived value of advanced subject degrees among those holding such degrees.

University of Missouri-Columbia

To establish a postgraduate internship program for librarians new to the profession.

University of Pittsburgh

To cover partially the publishing costs of a book on library leadership.

University of South Carolina

To study the learning styles of university librarians engaged in database searching, to aid in establishing more effective training programs for searchers.

University of Wisconsin-Madison

To complete a two-year academic program to improve problem-recognition and problem-solving capabilities of librarians through training and research methods.

Yale University

To recruit Yale undergraduates for the Yale Library Internship Program.

**Faculty/Librarian Cooperative Research Projects
1985-1987 Grants Active in Fiscal 1988*****Daniel Boyarski and Henry A. Pisciotta, Carnegie Mellon University***

To produce a graphic database searching tutorial that will be used to teach individuals how to employ basic database searching techniques.

Katherine Chiang, Howard Curtis, Linda Stewart, and J. Robert Cooke, Cornell University

To test the use of microcomputer technology for supporting access to large bibliographic data files and to make a MEDLARS database subset available to users.

Michael L. Tomlan and Judith Holliday, Cornell University

To search for certain nineteenth-century American architectural periodicals held outside research libraries.

Sara Penhale and Jerome H. Woolpy, Earlham College

To study the use of online abstracts as a source of information for undergraduate research.

Joseph McDonald and Lynda Micikas, Holy Family College

To develop and test a method of syllabus analysis as a way for faculty to participate in collection development.

Richard Busch, Liang-tseng Fan, M. Dale Hawley, Delbert Mueller, and Robert Schwarzwald, Kansas State University

To develop a method of improving access to NTIS reports on microfiche, and evaluate the potential of this approach for improving library service.

Danny P. Wallace, Alma Dawson, and Bert Boyce, Louisiana State University

To develop a core library collection for library automation by creating a set of lists of monographs and serials relevant to education for library automation and proposing a procedure for maintaining current records.

Rich Hines and Candy Schwartz, Massachusetts Institute of Technology

To plan, develop, and implement an online gateway between library users and MIT library systems and services.

Celia Wall, John Griffin, and Roger Haney, Murray State University

To study the effects in small liberal arts colleges of the availability of online databases upon the continuation of subscriptions for the printed versions of the same databases.

Gilbert Krulee and Brian Nielsen, Northwestern University

To develop an intelligent support system for the reference librarian, using artificial intelligence techniques to respond to natural language queries.

Marianne Cooper and Shoshana Kaufmann, Queens College of the City University of New York

To examine the relationships between library schools and academic libraries in the same institutions, and to identify factors that encourage or hinder development of cooperative efforts.

Thomas T. Surprenant, Queens College, Barbara Moran, University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, and Merrily Taylor, Brown University

To explore the role of the library in Brown University's efforts to incorporate electronic technologies in teaching, learning, and research.

Arthur Downing and Daniel O'Connor, Rutgers University

To study undergraduates' preferences for the number of bibliographic citations obtained through online searching.

Steven Atkinson and Geraldine Walker, State University of New York at Albany

To use measures of search recall to compare the coverage of different online databases and the effectiveness of natural language and controlled vocabulary for online retrieval for research in the humanities.

Richard S. Halsey and Ruth Fraley, State University of New York at Albany

To conduct a market study of the information needs of scholars in the public affairs and policy department at Rockefeller College, SUNY-Albany.

Nancy B. Nuzzo and William E. McGrath, State University of New York at Buffalo

To validate statistically the Research Libraries Group Conspectus for music.

Howard Pikoff and James Pomerantz, State University of New York at Buffalo

To develop and evaluate a faculty notification system in which RLG acquisitions lists will be used in combination with limited document retrieval to improve access to new interdisciplinary holdings.

Susan Bonzi and Dorcas MacDonald, Syracuse University

To study the effect of online bibliographic retrieval services on the quality of service provided by an interlibrary loan department, as well as costs and cost-effectiveness of online ordering services.

David Stam and Michael Nilan, Syracuse University

To prepare for reorganization planning by assessing the library system from the perspectives of library users and library staff.

Gloriana St. Clair and Rose Mary Magrill, Texas A&M University

To study undergraduate use of a library's collection by identifying and analyzing patterns of use of library materials across class levels and disciplines.

Dorothy McGarry, University of California, Los Angeles, and Sheila Intner, Simmons College

To analyze the fullness and accuracy of member-contributed cataloging in OCLC and RLIN.

James Danowski, Robert Daugherty, and Stephen Wiberley, University of Illinois at Chicago

To evaluate user persistence in scanning online public access catalog postings by determining whether most online catalog users abandon a search after a certain number of postings.

Herbert Goldbor, David Self, and Priscilla Smiley, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

To determine the extent of in-house use of library materials in a scientific library.

Carolyn O. Frost and Bonnie A. Dede, University of Michigan

To test subject heading compatibility between the Library of Congress Subject Headings and the University Library's catalog for automated authority control.

Jin Moo Choi and Nancy Washington, University of South Carolina

To study the learning styles of university librarians and the implications for their professional development.

Mark Rorvig, Allison Beck, and David Gracy, University of Texas at Austin

To create a digitized, facsimile version of graphic images in the University's collections and to measure users' reactions to the product.

Mark Kinnucan, Henry Overduin, Victoria Ripley, and Elizabeth Howes, University of Western Ontario

To enhance a test collection of online public access catalog records with tables of contents, for the purpose of upgrading search and retrieval effectiveness.

James H. Sweetland and Wilfred Fong, University of Wisconsin, Milwaukee

To evaluate the effects of book reviews on library purchasing decisions.

Ralph A. Gustafson, Ronald J. Chepesiuk, and Gloria Kelley, Winthrop College

To evaluate the effectiveness of several chemicals against mold growth (mildew) in library collections.

1987/1988 Faculty/Librarian Cooperative Research Grants

Arlene G. Taylor and Angela Giral, Columbia University

To determine the overlap between the *Avery Index to Architectural Periodicals* and the *Architectural Periodicals Index*.

Mary Biggs, Columbia University, and Victor Biggs, Brookdale Foundation

To explore the attitudes and experiences of library school faculty regarding research and publishing.

Joseph McDonald and Lynda B. Micikas, Holy Family College

To test a previously developed prototype method of analyzing syllabi as a way to identify collection strengths and weaknesses and encourage faculty participation in collection development.

Rita Millican and Michael Carpenter, Louisiana State University

To explore methods of recognizing depreciation of library collections.

Beth Paskoff and Anna Perrault, Louisiana State University

To use shelflist sampling in four university libraries to construct multi-dimensional profiles as a possible basis for cooperative collection development.

Shirley Fondiller, Mid-Atlantic Regional Nursing Association, and Jeanne D. Fonseca, Interagency Council on Library Resources for Nursing

To compile an inventory of libraries and archives that hold historical papers and documents on nursing and nurses.

Barbara Stein, North Texas State University, and Julia Rholes, Texas A&M University

To compare the cognitive styles of reference librarians and students in database searching classes to aid in the selection and training of online searchers.

Mary Grosch, Northern Illinois University, and Terry L. Weech, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

To determine the perceived value of advanced subject degrees by librarians who hold such degrees.

Marjorie Murfin, Ohio State University, and Charles A. Bunge, University of Wisconsin-Madison

To build a cost effectiveness model into a previously developed reference survey instrument.

Caryn Carr and Gaynelle Winograd, Pennsylvania State University

To assess the needs and perceptions of library users affiliated with the department of speech communication, as part of a collection development effort in that field.

Carol Tenopir and Christine Tomoyasu, University of Hawaii at Manoa

To study library users of full-text databases and to determine how such databases will be used in libraries.

Barbara Finkelstein and Danuta A. Nitecki, University of Maryland

To compare two microcomputer-based systems for use by teachers in evaluating potential curricular materials.

Ridley R. Kessler, Jr., and Evelyn H. Daniel, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

To study the U.S. regional depository libraries to establish baseline data and to determine the relationship of these libraries to one another and to the library community.

Jerry D. Saye and Eric C. Palo, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

To examine the relationship of subject-related online catalog searches to circulation patterns and profiles of the collection.

Susan E. Searing and Margo Anderson, University of Wisconsin

To examine the information-seeking behaviors of scholars in Women's Studies.

Program Meetings, 1987/1988

Academic Library Management Intern Program Selection Committee

February 16, 1988 (Washington, D.C.)

March 14, 1988 (Washington, D.C.)

Preservation

At the end of the 1988 fiscal year, the Commission on Preservation and Access, created in 1986 by CLR following a two-year study of the scope of national preservation needs, became an independent body. (Members of the Commission are listed on page 45.) As a separate organization, the Commission will retain ties to CLR, and the CLR president will serve as a member of the Commission's Board of Directors.

With the arrival in August 1987 of the Commission's first president, Patricia Battin, the work of the organization expanded, and two immediate tasks emerged: responding to increased Congressional interest in funding a nationwide preservation microfilming program through the National Endowment for the Humanities' Office of Preservation, and seeking nongovernmental funding for the Commission's programs. At the same time, development of a structure for a nationwide preservation microfilming program continued, and the Commission president met with a broad spectrum of leaders in the university, academic library, foundation, and government communities.

By the end of the fiscal year, Congressional funding for a national brittle books program was close to becoming a reality. Rep. Sidney R. Yates (D-Ill.), Chairman of the House of Representatives Appropriations Subcommittee on Interior and Related Agencies (which oversees appropriations for NEH), held hearings in March and April on the proposed nationwide filming program as part of his Subcommittee's consideration of NEH funding for the new federal fiscal year. The Commission, represented by Patricia Battin and chairman Billy Frye, was one of several academic, library, and charitable organizations asked to testify at both hearings. As a result, the Yates Subcommittee voted \$12.5 million in funding for the Office of Preservation, which represented an increase of \$8 million over the previous year's \$4.5 million appropriation. As proposed in a multiyear "capability budget" prepared by NEH at Mr. Yates's request, the \$12.5 million amount would increase proportionately each year through 1993, at which time some \$20 million would be available annually for preservation of deteriorating research library materials. Although signs were good at the year's end that the funding would be signed into law by the President, the recognition by Congress and government of the national sig-

nificance of the brittle books issue was in itself an important accomplishment of the Commission and related organizations during the past year.

The Commission was also successful in generating new funding for research and demonstration projects. In addition to a \$300,000 grant from The William and Flora Hewlett Foundation earlier in the year, the Commission received in March a grant of \$1.5 million from The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation. The Mellon grant was for a five-year period of project-related activities. These two grants supplemented continued funding from the Council on Library Resources, The H. W. Wilson Foundation, and the universities that were the original funders of the Commission: Columbia University, Harvard University, Indiana University, Princeton University, Stanford University, the University of California at Berkeley, the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, the University of Michigan, Yale University, and the institutions of the New York State Preservation Program.

Central to the Commission's ongoing work during the year was the development of increased clarity about the structure of a nationwide preservation microfilming program. In pursuit of this objective, the Commission favors a national, collaborative microfilming program resulting in the preservation of a representative core of materials that will otherwise be lost by the turn of the century. Within the preservation program, significant issues reflecting the fundamental changes in the nation's scholarly information systems must be addressed. These issues include effective collaborative efforts, knowledge of disciplinary research methods, choice of format for preserved materials, criteria for selection, bibliographic control mechanisms, use of new technologies, copyright implications, network standards, compatibility and access, management of systems of distributed access, the role of the commercial sector, and new financing strategies. Another function of the Commission is to encourage consensus on minimal requirements for international collaboration in preserving the published heritage via archival microfilming (or other proved means), with ample allowance for local options at local expense. Such collaboration will be built on a basic principle: creation of a new master copy, using an archival technology that will insure access.

In addition to the microfilming program, which is primarily reactive, insuring the preservation of the human record in all formats also requires proactive efforts. Since so much of the human record is, and continues to be, printed on acidic paper, the most critical proactive response is to encourage the increasing use of acid-free paper in all publishing that is meant to be available to succeeding generations. Technology now exists to convert acid-paper-producing mills to alkaline-paper production, and increasing numbers of manufacturers are doing so. Building on past efforts in this arena, the Commission worked in the past year to establish links with commercial and university publishers, writers, and paper manufacturers to encourage the increased production and use of alkaline paper.

The problem of deteriorating scientific literature was addressed in a day-long meeting sponsored by the Commission in October 1987. Medical and

scientific literature often requires coated paper for proper display of graphic information, and most coated paper used in such publications is acidic.

A variety of projects were funded during the year, including support for broadcasting the preservation film, "Slow Fires," on the national Public Broadcasting System. The film won a Golden Eagle award from the CINE documentary film organization. Also funded was a project to determine the feasibility of developing an international database of bibliographic records of materials on microfilm, as part of the effort to avoid, where possible, duplication of preservation microfilming efforts in Europe and the United States. A technical project receiving Commission funding was a Mid-Atlantic Preservation Service proposal to develop archival standards for the use of 105mm microfiche film. The Commission also launched an informal monthly newsletter, to be circulated primarily to Association of Research Libraries member institutions.

Finally, the coming year will be affected greatly by the final decisions regarding increased federal funding for the nationwide preservation effort, and the intensive development work that will occur to launch the program successfully. In addition, the Commission will be operating as an independent nonprofit corporation and will, beginning with the 1988 fiscal year, publish its own annual report.

Preservation Projects Active in 1987/1988

American Film Foundation

To produce a half-hour version of the preservation film "Slow Fires."

Brigham Young University

To develop a prototype of The Conservator, a nondamaging book return unit.

Educational Broadcasting Corporation

For public broadcast of the film "Slow Fires."

Robert M. Hayes

To obtain data relating to the costs of preservation and overlap of collections in several Association of Research Libraries member institutions.

International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions

To support partially a joint colloquium on newspaper resource sharing.

Library of Congress

To fund travel costs for selected participants in an international conference on preservation of library materials.

Library of Congress

To complete and distribute copies of a series of training videotapes on library preservation.

Mid-Atlantic Preservation Service

To study production standards required for 105mm archival microfiche.

Mid-Atlantic Preservation Service

To provide start-up and capital equipment support for the Mid-Atlantic Preservation Service.

National Information Standards Organization

For development of an American National Standard for hard cover edition bindings.

Hans Rütimann

To stimulate and assist with the development of an international bibliographic records database on preservation activity.

University of Illinois, Urbana-Champaign

To provide partial support for the 1988 Allerton Institute concerned with preservation of nonbook materials.

Program Meetings, 1987/1988**Commission on Preservation and Access**

September 24, 1987 (Washington, D.C.)

January 28, 1988 (Washington, D.C.)

April 27, 1988 (Washington, D.C.)

June 21, 1988 (Washington, D.C.)

Preservation of Scientific Literature

October 13, 1987 (Washington, D.C.)

Appendix A

Program Committees and Project Participants

ACADEMIC LIBRARY MANAGEMENT INTERN PROGRAM SELECTION COMMITTEE

Deanna Marcum (Chair)
Council on Library Resources
Millicent Abell
Yale University
Charles Churchwell
Wayne State University

Richard De Gennaro
New York Public Library
Susan Rhee
University of California, Berkeley
Duane Webster
Association of Research Libraries

BIBLIOGRAPHIC SERVICE DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM LINKED SYSTEMS PROJECT

LSP POLICY COMMITTEE

Henriette Avram
Library of Congress
David Bishop
University of Georgia
Rowland Brown
*OCLC Online Computer Library
Center*
Richard Dougherty
University of Michigan
(Resigned, September 1987)
Dorothy Gregor
University of California, San Diego

Mary Ellen Jacob
*OCLC Online Computer Library
Center*
James Michalko
The Research Libraries Group, Inc.
Carlton Rochell
New York University
(Beginning September 1987)
N. A. Stussy
Western Library Network
(Resigned, December 1987)
Bruce Ziegman
Western Library Network
(Beginning December 1987)

LSP TECHNICAL COMMITTEE

David Bishop (Chair)

University of Georgia

James Aagaard

Northwestern University Library

Edwin Buchinski

National Library of Canada

Wayne Davison

The Research Libraries Group, Inc.

Ray Denenberg

Library of Congress

Ron Jordan

*OCLC Online Computer Library**Center*

Larry Learn

*OCLC Online Computer Library**Center*

David Pcolar

Triangle Research Libraries Network

Robert Schultheisz

National Library of Medicine

Keith Thomas

Geac Computers International, Inc.

BIBLIOGRAPHIC SERVICES STUDY COMMITTEE

Carol Mandel (Chair)

Columbia University

Dorothy Gregor

University of California, San Diego

Paul Kantor

Tantalus Inc.

Martin Runkle

University of Chicago

COMMISSION ON PRESERVATION AND ACCESS

Billy Frye (Chair)

Emory University

Millicent Abell

Yale University

Herbert Bailey

Princeton University Press (retired)

James Govan

*University of North Carolina,
Chapel Hill*

Vartan Gregorian

New York Public Library

Kenneth Gros Louis

Indiana University

Carole Huxley

*New York State Education**Department*

Sidney Verba

Harvard University

William Welsh

Library of Congress

The Commission on Preservation and Access was formed in the spring of 1986 to continue the work of the CLR Committee on Preservation and Access. While the Commission is an independent body, CLR is providing financial and administrative support during the Commission's formative period. Funding for the first three years of the Commission's work is being

provided by CLR, The Getty Grant Program, The William and Flora Hewlett Foundation, The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, The H. W. Wilson Foundation, and the following:

Columbia University
 Harvard University
 Indiana University
 Princeton University
 Stanford University
 University of California, Berkeley
 University of Illinois, Urbana-Champaign
 University of Michigan
 Yale University

Participants in the New York State Preservation Program

RESEARCH LIBRARY COMMITTEE

Millicent Abell <i>Yale University</i>	William Joyce <i>Princeton University</i>
William Arms <i>Carnegie Mellon University</i>	Beverly Lynch <i>University of Illinois at Chicago</i>
Patricia Battin <i>Commission on Preservation and Access</i>	Theodore Marmor <i>Russell Sage Foundation; Yale University</i>
Phyllis Bober <i>Bryn Mawr College</i>	Robert Middlekauff <i>University of California, Berkeley</i>
Edwin Bridges <i>Alabama Department of Archives</i>	J. Hillis Miller <i>University of California, Irvine</i>
Bernard C. Cohen <i>University of Wisconsin</i>	Robert O'Neil <i>University of Virginia</i>
Bernard S. Cohn <i>University of Chicago</i>	James N. Rosse <i>Stanford University</i>
Jill Conway <i>Massachusetts Institute of Technology; American Antiquarian Society</i>	Neil Rudenstine <i>Andrew W. Mellon Foundation</i>
John D'Arms <i>University of Michigan</i>	George Rupp <i>Rice University</i>
James O. Freedman <i>Dartmouth College</i>	Robert A. Skotheim <i>Whitman College</i>
Billy E. Frye <i>Emory University</i>	Sidney Verba <i>Harvard University</i>
James Govan <i>University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill</i>	Charles Young <i>University of California, Los Angeles</i>

Appendix B

Publications and Reports Resulting From CLR Programs, 1987/1988

Part I. Publications of the Council and CLR Staff

Battin, Patricia M. "Preserving America's National Heritage: The Response of the Commission on Preservation and Access." In *The Bowker Annual of Library and Book Trade Information*, 33d ed., 88-91. New York: Bowker, 1988.

Haas, Warren J. "IFLA and CLR, 1971-1987." *IFLA Journal* 13 (1987): 227-28.

———. "Information Studies, Librarianship, and Professional Leadership." *Bulletin of the Medical Library Association* 76 (January 1988): 1-6.

———. "National Preservation Programs." In *Preservation of Library Materials: Conference Held at the National Library of Austria, Vienna, April 7-10, 1986*, vol. 1, edited by Merrily A. Smith, 112-18. IFLA Publications 41. München: K.G. Saur for International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions, 1987.

———. "The Program of the Council on Library Resources." In *Les Bibliothèques: tradition et mutation: mélanges offerts à Jean-Pierre Clavel à*

l'occasion de son 65e anniversaire, 91-101. Lausanne, Switzerland: Bibliothèque cantonale et universitaire, 1987.

Thompson, Mary Agnes. "Council on Library Resources." In *The Bowker Annual of Library and Book Trade Information*, 33d ed., 222-25. New York: Bowker, 1988.

Part II. Publications by Grantees and Contractors

Albritton, Rosie L. "Leadership Development." *College & Research Libraries News* 48 (November 1987): 618-23.

Allen, Bryce. "Bibliographic and Text-Linguistic Schemata in the User-Intermediary Interaction." Ph.D. diss., University of Western Ontario, 1988.

Avram, Henriette D., and Beacher Wiggins. "The National Coordinated Cataloging Program." *Library Resources and Technical Services* 32 (April 1988): 111-15.

Biggs, Mary, and Victor Biggs. "Reference Collection Development in Academic Libraries: Report of a Survey." *RQ* 27, no. 1 (Fall 1987): 67-79.

Cress, Elizabeth J., and Donald A. Cress, eds. *A Guide to Rare and Out-of-Print Books in the Vatican Film Library*. Lanham, Md.: University Press of America, 1986.

Davidson, Lloyd, and Julie Hurd. "A Study of the Use of CAS Online at an Academic Research Institution under the Conditions of Free Access: Data from an Analysis of Monthly Billing Invoices." In *ASIS '87: Proceedings of the 50th ASIS Annual Meeting*, vol. 24, edited by Ching-chih Chen and Toni Carbo Bearman, 46-53. Medford, N.J.: Learned Information, 1987.

Denenberg, Ray. "The Linked Systems Project and the Maturing of Open Systems Interconnection." *Library Hi Tech News* no. 48 (April 1988): 1-3.

Fenly, Judith F., and Beacher Wiggins, comps. and eds. *The Linked Systems Project: A Networking Tool for Libraries*. Dublin, Ohio: OCLC Online Computer Library Center, 1988.

Ferguson, Anthony W., Joan Grant, and Joel S. Rutstein. "The RLG Conspectus: Its Uses and Benefits." *College & Research Libraries* 49 (May 1988): 197-206.

Gothberg, Helen M., and Donald E. Riggs. "Time Management in Academic Libraries." *College & Research Libraries* 49 (March 1988): 131-40.

Issues in Research Librarianship: Proceedings of a Forum Series. Co-Sponsored by Indiana University Libraries, Bloomington, and Indiana University School of Library and Information Science, January-April 1987. Bloomington: Indiana University Libraries, 1987.

McGill, Michael J., Larry L. Learn,

and Thomas K. G. Lydon. "A Technical Evaluation of the LSP Protocols in the Name Authority Distribution Application." *Information Technology and Libraries* 6 (December 1987): 253-65.

Morton, Herbert C., Judith Mayers, Anne J. Price, Jane Rosenberg, Deborah Styles, Carol Tenopir, and Bettina Hogen. *Writings on Scholarly Communication: An Annotated Bibliography of Books and Articles on Publishing, Libraries, Scholarly Research and Related Issues*. Washington, D.C.: Office of Scholarly Communication and Technology, American Council of Learned Societies, 1988.

Murfin, Marjorie E., and Charles A. Bunge. "Paraprofessionals at the Reference Desk." *Journal of Academic Librarianship* 14 (March 1988): 10-14.

"NACO/LSP Contribution Begins with Yale." *Library of Congress Information Bulletin* 46 (October 12, 1987): 438 + .

"National Coordinated Cataloging Program Pilot Project to Begin in 1988." *Library of Congress Information Bulletin* 46 (October 19, 1987): 449-50.

Person, Ruth J., and George C. Newman. *Selection of the University Librarian*. OMS Occasional Paper, no. 13. Washington, D.C.: Office of Management Studies, Association of Research Libraries, 1988.

Picturescope 32, no. 4 (Winter 1987): entire issue. Special issue on photo preservation, published by the Picture Division, Special Libraries Association.

Pollard, Richard. "Microcomputer Database Management Systems for Bibliographic Data." *The Electronic*

- Library* 4, no. 4 (August 1986): 230-40.
- Preservation of Library Materials: Conference Held at the National Library of Austria, Vienna, April 7-10, 1986.* Edited by Merrily A. Smith. 2 vols. IFLA Publications 41. München: K.G. Saur for International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions, 1987.
- Rorvig, Mark E. "Psychometric Measurement and Information Retrieval." In *Annual Review of Information Science and Technology*, vol. 23, edited by Martha E. Williams, 157-89. Amsterdam: Elsevier Scientific Publishers for the American Society for Information Science, 1988.
- Slow Fires: On the Preservation of the Human Record.* 16mm, 58 min. 1987. Distributed by American Film Foundation, Santa Monica, Calif.
- Slow Fires: On the Preservation of the Human Record.* 16mm, 30 min. 1987. Distributed by American Film Foundation, Santa Monica, Calif.
- Townley, Charles T. *Human Relations in Library Network Development.* Hamden, Conn.: Shoe String Press, Library Professional Publication, 1988.
- Wiberley, Stephen E., Jr., and Robert Allen Daugherty. "Users' Persistence in Scanning Lists of References." *College & Research Libraries* 49 (March 1988): 149-56.
- Woodsworth, Anne. "Chief Information Officers on Campus." *EDUCOM Bulletin* 22 (Summer 1987): 2-4.
- . "Libraries and the Chief Information Officer: Implications and Trends." *Library Hi Tech* 6 (1988): 37-44.
- Woodsworth, Anne, and Barbara von Wahlde, eds. *Leadership for Research Libraries: A Festschrift for Robert M. Hayes.* Metuchen, N.J.: Scarecrow Press, 1988.
- Part III. Project Reports Received**
- Many project reports are published in the professional literature. Authors retain ownership of the reports and are asked to submit copies to the ERIC database. ERIC document numbers that have been reported to CLR are listed at the end of the citation. Inquiries about reports without an ERIC number should be addressed to the author.
- "Analysis of Searching: Bibliographic and Authority Records—WLN, RLG, OCLC, LC." Washington, D.C.: Library of Congress, January 1988.
- Bonzi, Susan, and Dorcas MacDonald. "The Effect of Computerized Bibliographic Retrieval Services on the Quality of an Interlibrary Loan Department: No Cause for Alarm." Syracuse University, December 1987. (Cooperative Research Project Report)
- Chan, Lois M., and Richard Pollard. "Bibliographic Guide to Indexing Languages Used in Online Databases." University of Kentucky, May 1988. (Guide to be published.)
- Chiang, Katherine, et al. "Advanced Microcomputer Technology Supporting Large Bibliographic Data Files." Cornell University, November 1987. (Cooperative Research Project Report)
- Cooper, Marianne, and Shoshana Kaufmann. "Librarians and Li-

- brary Educators in the 1980's: Shared Interests, Cooperative Ventures." Queens College, CUNY, December 1987. (Cooperative Research Project Report)
- . "Library Schools and their Host Academic Libraries: Relationships, Power, Perceptions." Queens College, CUNY, September 1987. (Cooperative Research Project Report)
- Cravey, Pamela J. "Occupational Role Identity and Occupational Role Image in Four Subspecialties of Librarianship." Georgia State University, February 1988.
- Frost, Carolyn O., and Bonnie A. Dede. "Subject Heading Compatibility between LCSH and Catalog Files of a Large Research Library: A Suggested Model for Analysis." University of Michigan, October 1987. (Cooperative Research Project Report)
- Goldhor, Herbert, Kathleen Roegge, and Priscilla Smiley. "The In-House Use of Materials in a Veterinary Medicine Library." University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, December 1987. (Cooperative Research Project Report)
- Hayes, Robert M. "The Magnitude, Costs, and Benefits of the Preservation of Brittle Books." Sherman Oaks, Calif., November 1987.
- Holliday, Judith, and Michael A. Tomlan. "Nineteenth-Century American Architectural Periodicals." Cornell University, December 1986. (Cooperative Research Project Report)
- Kinnucan, Mark, and Xin Lu. "Tables of Contents in Online Catalogs: Final Report to OCLC and the Council on Library Resources." University of Western Ontario, 1988. (Cooperative Research Project Report)
- McGrath, William E., and Nancy Nuzzo. "Statistical Validation of the Research Libraries Group Conspectus for Music." SUNY-Buffalo, September 1987. (Cooperative Research Project Report)
- Penhale, Sara, Jerome H. Woolpy, and William H. Buskirk. "Online Abstracts as a Source of Information for Undergraduate Research in a Small College Library." Earlham College, July 1987. (Cooperative Research Project Report)
- "Review of Bibliographic Record Standards and Related Issues." Washington, D.C.: Library of Congress, October 1987.
- St. Clair, Gloriana, and Rose Mary Magrill. "Undergraduate Use of Collections in the Production of Term Papers: Preliminary Results" (ALA poster session). Texas A&M University, 1988. (Cooperative Research Project Report)
- Sweetland, James, and Wilfred Fong. "Library Holdings and Reviews of Reference Books." University of Wisconsin-Milwaukee, February 1988. (Cooperative Research Project Report)
- Wall, Celia, Roger D. Haney, and John B. Griffin. "Hard Copy vs. Online: A Survey of Small Liberal Arts Colleges." Murray State University, 1988. (Cooperative Research Project Report)
- Yu, Priscilla C. "Collection Development of Western Language Materials in Chinese Libraries: A Study of Four Libraries." University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, May 1986.

Appendix C

Program Guidelines and Grant Application Procedures

The Council on Library Resources supports work by individuals and organizations on matters pertinent to library service and information systems, with the primary objective of improving the quality and performance of academic and research libraries. Individuals with specific interests and expertise are encouraged to take the initiative and propose for consideration projects within the broad areas of the Council's program, as described in this report.

In addition, CLR sponsors special programs, such as that offering support for cooperative research projects involving librarians and teaching faculty. Such programs are described in brochures available from CLR.

Application Procedures

Initial inquiries should state the purpose of the proposed work, indicate methodology, establish the credentials of the responsible individuals, and provide an estimate of total costs and funding requirements. CLR will respond promptly with an indication of interest. If subsequent exploration seems justified, preparation of a complete proposal will be suggested. Full documentation should include:

1. A concise description of the proposed project.
2. A thorough explanation of the work to be done, including objectives and methods to be employed. A timetable, pertinent background information, and plans for evaluation of results should also be provided.
3. A detailed budget linking costs to project components.
4. Curricula vitae of the principal investigators.

Proposals are carefully reviewed by CLR staff and, when necessary, external advisors, who consider such matters as relevance to current CLR interests and activities; relationship to other, similar work; projected costs in the context of the work described; and importance of anticipated results. The Council also looks for evidence of institutional support, including cost sharing. With the exception of a few cyclical programs, there are no submission deadlines.

Support is not provided for construction or renovation, collection acquisitions, routine operating costs, activities judged to be of limited influence, or work that essentially repeats previous research. CLR does not fund indirect costs or, with rare exceptions, equipment purchases. While CLR, in consultation with its advisors, often initiates and promotes work in program areas, exploratory correspondence and conversation are always welcome, and all proposals receive careful consideration.

All inquiries should be addressed to Council on Library Resources, 1785 Massachusetts Avenue, N.W., Washington, D.C. 20036.

ACTIVE PROJECTS

FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

Acknowledgement

The following pages record grants and contracts active during fiscal year 1988 and, through audited financial reports, provide an overall picture of CLR income and expenditures.

Financial support for CLR activities comes from many sources. On behalf of the academic and research library community, we express gratitude to:

The Ford Foundation
The J. Paul Getty Trust
The William and Flora Hewlett Foundation
The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation
The Pew Charitable Trusts
The Alfred P. Sloan Foundation
The H. W. Wilson Foundation

We also acknowledge the support for the Commission on Preservation and Access from the universities listed on page 46 of this report.

Grants and Contracts Active in Fiscal 1988 (unaudited)

	FY 1988			
	Unpaid 6/30/87	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/88
American Antiquarian Society				
Worcester, Mass.				
Completion of the North American Imprints Program	\$ 15,000	\$ -0-	\$ -0-	\$ 15,000
American Film Foundation				
Santa Monica, Calif.				
To produce a half-hour version of the preservation film "Slow Fires"	4,000	-0-	4,000	-0-
American Historical Association				
Washington, D.C.				
Planning meeting for a new <i>Guide to Historical Literature</i>	6,780	(1,459)	5,321	-0-
American Nurses Foundation, Inc.				
Kansas City, Mo.				
Assembling a guide to archival sources in nursing	-0-	3,000	3,000	-0-
Association of Research Libraries				
Washington, D.C.				
ARL long-range planning	-0-	10,000	10,000	-0-
Institute for library educators				
Second—1986	5,857	-0-	5,857	-0-
Third—1988	25,000	-0-	-0-	25,000
Trudi Bellardo				
Washington, D.C.				
History of online information retrieval systems	1,000	-0-	900	100

FY 1988				
	Unpaid 6/30/87	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/88
Mary Biggs & Victor Biggs				
New York, N.Y.				
Study of attitudes and experiences of library school faculty on scholarly communication	-0-	2,741	2,741	-0-
Brigham Young University				
Provo, Utah				
The Conservator, a non-damaging book return unit	-0-	3,000	3,000	-0-
The British Library				
London, England				
Publish the proceedings of the International Conference on Japanese Information	-0-	5,000	5,000	-0-
Carnegie Mellon University				
Pittsburgh, Pa.				
Establish a study group on the structure of electronic text	3,000	-0-	-0-	3,000
Columbia University				
New York, N.Y.				
Empirical study of the overlap between the <i>Avery Index to Architectural Periodicals</i> and the <i>Architectural Periodicals Index</i>	-0-	2,990	-0-	2,990
Library fellows program	24,450	-0-	-0-	24,450
Measuring the public services impact of an online catalog	11,200	-0-	-0-	11,200
Educational Broadcasting Corporation				
New York, N.Y.				
Public broadcast of the film "Slow Fires"	-0-	14,950	14,950	-0-

	FY 1988			Unpaid 6/30/88
	Unpaid 6/30/87	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	
Enoch Pratt Free Library				
Baltimore, Md.				
Centennial symposium	1,000	-0-	-0-	1,000
European Foundation for Library Cooperation				
The Hague, Netherlands				
Development funds	1,000	-0-	-0-	1,000
Georgia State University				
Atlanta, Ga.				
Study of occupational role identity and image of subspecialties in librarianship	649	(7)	642	-0-
Robert M. Hayes				
Los Angeles, Calif.				
Study of preservation costs and benefits	20,100	(27,715)	(7,615)	-0-
Holy Family College				
Philadelphia, Pa.				
Syllabus analysis for faculty participation in collection development	1,466	-0-	1,466	-0-
To test a method of faculty syllabus analysis	-0-	2,782	2,782	-0-
Indiana University				
Bloomington, Ind.				
Papers for a forum series on research librarianship	1,000	(761)	239	-0-
International Association of School Librarianship				
Kalamazoo, Mich.				
Partial support for the 17th Annual Conference	-0-	250	250	-0-

	FY 1988			
	Unpaid 6/30/87	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/88
International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions The Hague, Netherlands				
Joint Colloquium on Newspaper Resource Sharing	-0-	11,700	-0-	11,700
Kansas State University Manhattan, Kans.				
Development of a method of improving access to NTIS reports on microfiche	2,807	-0-	2,807	-0-
Library of Congress Washington, D.C.				
Bibliographic analysis— Linked Systems Project	1,620	-0-	1,620	-0-
Conference on libraries and scholarly communication	-0-	10,000	10,000	-0-
Completion of a series of training videotapes on library preservation	1,110	-0-	-0-	1,110
International conference on preservation of library materials	2,250	-0-	2,250	-0-
Louisiana State University Baton Rouge, La.				
To construct collection profiles of academic libraries	-0-	3,000	3,000	-0-
Development of a curriculum for library systems analysts	14,000	(4,494)	9,506	-0-
To explore methods of recognizing depreciation of library materials	-0-	2,983	2,983	-0-
Massachusetts Institute of Technology Cambridge, Mass.				
Development and implementation of an online gateway between library users and MIT library services	3,000	-0-	3,000	-0-

	FY 1988			
	Unpaid 6/30/87	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/88
Mid-Atlantic Preservation Service				
Bethlehem, Pa.				
Start-up and capital equipment support	-0-	47,956	47,956	-0-
Study of microfiche production standards	-0-	24,131	-0-	24,131
National Information Standards Organization				
Gaithersburg, Md.				
Development of an American national standard for hardcover edition bindings	23,738	-0-	3,038	20,700
U.S. representation at an international meeting on paper permanence	-0-	2,000	-0-	2,000
North Texas State University				
Denton, Tex.				
Study of selection and training of online searchers	-0-	3,000	3,000	-0-
Northwestern University				
Evanston, Ill.				
Implementation of the standard network interconnection in a local library system	10,000	-0-	10,000	-0-
OCLC Online Computer Library Center				
Dublin, Ohio				
Increase accessibility of Library of Congress subject headings in online bibliographic systems	93,700	-0-	30,000	63,700
Ohio State University				
Columbus, Ohio				
Develop a cost effectiveness model for reference service	-0-	3,000	3,000	-0-

	FY 1988			
	Unpaid 6/30/87	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/88
Pennsylvania State University				
University Park, Pa.				
Study of library consortial relationships	500	-0-	500	-0-
Study of user needs in the field of speech communication	-0-	2,968	-0-	2,968
The Research Libraries Group, Inc.				
Stanford, Calif.				
Analysis of the RLG Conspectus as a collection management tool	5,500	-0-	5,500	-0-
Bibliographic analysis— Linked Systems Project	6,470	-0-	6,470	-0-
Creation of a national database of public records information	532	-0-	-0-	532
Joint project for authorities implementation	89,245	-0-	89,245	-0-
Travel support for RLG archives committee	3,992	(2,622)	1,370	-0-
Hans Rütimann				
New York, N.Y.				
Development of an international bibliographic records database on preservation activity	-0-	50,000	-0-	50,000
Simmons College				
Boston, Mass.				
Symposium on solutions to the problems of recruiting, educating, and training cataloging librarians	-0-	15,000	-0-	15,000
Stanford University				
Stanford, Calif.				
Investigation of end-user searching of bibliographic databases	4,300	(591)	3,709	-0-

	FY 1988			
	Unpaid 6/30/87	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/88
State University of New York				
Albany, N.Y.				
To publish the proceedings of an international conference on classification in the computer age	-0-	2,000	-0-	2,000
Study of online database research in the humanities	3,000	-0-	3,000	-0-
State University of New York				
Buffalo, N.Y.				
Study of RLG acquisitions lists to improve access to new interdisciplinary holdings	3,000	-0-	3,000	-0-
Abigail Dahl-Hansen Studdiford				
Bridgewater, N.J.				
Study of public policy issues relating to research libraries	8,000	-0-	-0-	8,000
Syracuse University				
Syracuse, N.Y.				
Textual analysis of information needs derived from abstracts of documents	11,913	-0-	10,000	1,913
University of California				
Los Angeles, Calif.				
Conference on conceptual foundations of cataloging	3,670	-0-	-0-	3,670
Study of microcomputer- based digital imaging as a technique for preservation of library materials	-0-	20,500	18,000	2,500
Research program: long-range strategic planning for libraries and information resources in research universities	350,000	-0-	-0-	350,000
Senior fellows conference— 1988	-0-	25,000	-0-	25,000

	FY 1988			
	Unpaid 6/30/87	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/88
Senior fellows program—				
1987	45,000	(22,846)	40,000 (17,846)	-0-
1989	-0-	30,000	-0-	30,000
University of Chicago				
Chicago, Ill.				
Implementation of a concentration in library automation and information systems	39,500	-0-	39,500	-0-
Multi-institutional professional development program for recent library school graduates	12,221	-0-	-0-	12,221
University of Georgia				
Athens, Ga.				
Internships for recent library school graduates	63,098	-0-	9,517	53,581
University of Hawaii, Manoa				
Honolulu, Hawaii				
To study users of full-text databases	-0-	2,988	-0-	2,988
University of Illinois				
Chicago, Ill.				
Study of library users' persistence in scanning online catalog postings	1,200	-0-	1,200	-0-
Study of strategic planning issues for the research university	69,200	-0-	29,000	40,200
University of Illinois				
Urbana, Ill.				
1988 Allerton Institute	-0-	10,000	5,000	5,000
Developing and evaluating online catalog interface enhancements	8,000	-0-	-0-	8,000
Study of perceived values of advanced subject degrees	-0-	3,000	-0-	3,000

	FY 1988			
	Unpaid 6/30/87	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/88
University of Kentucky				
Lexington, Ky.				
Bibliographic guide to indexing languages used in online databases	2,580	-0-	2,580	-0-
University of Maryland				
College Park, Md.				
To evaluate software for identification of curriculum information	-0-	3,000	3,000	-0-
University of Michigan				
Ann Arbor, Mich.				
Increase accessibility of Library of Congress subject headings in online bibliographic systems	47,925	-0-	25,000	22,925
Second European Conference on Archives	-0-	10,000	-0-	10,000
University of Minnesota				
St. Paul, Minn.				
Plan and design a model academic integrated information center	117,000	-0-	100,000	17,000
University of Missouri				
Columbia, Mo.				
Internships for recent library school graduates	55,205	-0-	17,813	37,392
Study of information needs of philosophers	-0-	34,625	-0-	34,625
University of North Carolina				
at Chapel Hill				
Chapel Hill, N.C.				
Study of online catalog requests as a management information tool in collection development	-0-	2,980	2,980	-0-

	FY 1988			
	Unpaid 6/30/87	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/88
Study of the Regional Depository Library System	-0-	3,000	-0-	3,000
University of Pittsburgh Pittsburgh, Pa.				
Publication subvention	-0-	3,275 (775)	2,500	-0-
University of South Carolina Columbia, S.C.				
Study of learning styles of university librarians	2,960	-0-	2,960	-0-
University of Western Ontario London, Ontario, Canada				
Study of bibliographic and text-linguistic schemata in the user-intermediary interaction	-0-	1,990	1,490	500
University of Wisconsin Madison, Wis.				
Development of a supplementary education program for academic and research librarians	4,677	(5,314)	(637)	-0-
University of Wisconsin Milwaukee, Wis.				
Study of information- seeking behavior and information needs of researchers in women's studies	-0-	3,000	3,000	-0-
Yale University New Haven, Conn.				
Library internship program for Yale undergraduates	7,000	(677)	6,323	-0-
Undergraduate Internship Program	-0-	16,000	15,000	1,000

	FY 1988			
	Unpaid	Grants	Payments	Unpaid
	6/30/87	and Contracts	(Refunds)	6/30/88
		(Adjustments)		
Other refunds and adjustments from prior years' grants and contracts	-0-	(457)	(457)	-0-
Totals	\$1,239,415	\$391,809	\$639,965	\$950,096
		(67,718)	(26,555)	

Report of Independent Accountants

August 19, 1988

To the Board of Directors of
Council on Library Resources, Inc.

In our opinion, the accompanying balance sheets and the related statements of revenues, expenses and changes in fund balance, of changes in cash and short-term investments and of functional expenses present fairly, in all material respects, the financial position of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. at June 30, 1988 and 1987, and the results of its operations and its functional expenses for the year ended June 30, 1988 and the changes in its cash and short-term investments for the two years then ended in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles. These financial statements are the responsibility of the Council's management; our responsibility is to express an opinion on these financial statements based on our audits. We conducted our audits of these statements in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards which require that we plan and perform the audit to obtain reasonable assurance about whether the financial statements are free of material misstatement. An audit includes examining, on a test basis, evidence supporting the amounts and disclosures in the financial statements, assessing the accounting principles used and significant estimates made by management, and evaluating the overall financial statement presentation. We believe that our audits provide a reasonable basis for the opinion expressed above.

Price Waterhouse
Washington, D.C.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

Balance Sheets

	<u>1988</u>	<u>June 30</u> <u>1987</u>
ASSETS		
Cash and short-term investments, including restricted amounts of \$3,334,949 and \$1,494,143, respectively	\$6,527,756	\$4,357,102
Grants receivable (Note 2)		
Unrestricted	1,200,000	1,800,000
Restricted	1,390,500	2,383,164
Prepaid expenses and deposits	<u>13,228</u>	<u>12,475</u>
Total assets	<u>\$9,131,484</u>	<u>\$8,552,741</u>
LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE		
Deferred revenue (Note 2)		
Unrestricted	\$1,500,000	\$2,100,000
Restricted	3,900,419	2,700,613
Grants and contracts payable (Note 2)		
Unrestricted	125,066	62,721
Restricted	825,030	1,176,694
Accounts payable and accrued employee benefits	<u>76,790</u>	<u>60,586</u>
Total liabilities	<u>6,427,305</u>	<u>6,100,614</u>
Fund balance		
Appropriated	602,302	1,360,287
Unappropriated	<u>2,101,877</u>	<u>1,091,840</u>
Total fund balance	<u>2,704,179</u>	<u>2,452,127</u>
Total liabilities and fund balance	<u>\$9,131,484</u>	<u>\$8,552,741</u>

Statement of Revenues, Expenses and Changes in Fund Balance

FOR THE YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 1988
(With Comparative Totals for 1987)

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	<u>Restricted</u>	<u>Total 1988</u>	<u>Total 1987</u>
Revenues (Note 2)				
Grants and				
contracts	\$ 600,000	\$705,238	\$1,305,238	\$1,303,136
Contributions		139,062	139,062	58,861
Investment income	<u>308,584</u>	—	<u>308,584</u>	<u>253,430</u>
Total revenues	<u>908,584</u>	<u>844,300</u>	<u>1,752,884</u>	<u>1,615,427</u>
Expenses (Notes 2, 3 and 4)				
Program				
Research	22,983	333,329	356,312	449,182
Access	66,125	154,627	220,752	166,319
Bibliography	141,682		141,682	196,903
Librarianship	101,643	29,295	130,938	190,939
Preservation				
commission	<u>89,246</u>	<u>327,049</u>	<u>416,295</u>	<u>180,735</u>
Total program	421,679	844,300	1,265,979	1,184,078
Administration	<u>234,853</u>	—	<u>234,853</u>	<u>223,313</u>
Total expenses	<u>656,532</u>	<u>844,300</u>	<u>1,500,832</u>	<u>1,407,391</u>
Excess of revenues over expenses	252,052		252,052	208,036
Fund balance, begin- ning of year	<u>2,452,127</u>	—	<u>2,452,127</u>	<u>2,244,091</u>
Fund balance, end of year	<u>\$2,704,179</u>	<u>\$ —</u>	<u>\$2,704,179</u>	<u>\$2,452,127</u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

Statements of Changes in Cash and Short-term Investments

	<u>Year ended June 30</u>	
	<u>1988</u>	<u>1987</u>
Sources of cash and short-term investments		
Excess of revenues over expenses	\$ 252,052	\$ 208,036
Increase in deferred income	599,806	1,172,004
Decrease in grants receivable	1,592,664	
Increase in accounts payable and accrued benefits	16,204	19,734
	<u>2,460,726</u>	<u>1,399,774</u>
Uses of cash and short-term investments		
Increase in grants receivable		1,229,000
Decrease in grants and contracts payable	289,319	170,408
Other	753	5,627
	<u>290,072</u>	<u>1,405,035</u>
Increase (decrease) in cash and short-term investments	2,170,654	(5,261)
Cash and short-term investments, beginning of year	<u>4,357,102</u>	<u>4,362,363</u>
Cash and short-term investments, end of year	<u>\$6,527,756</u>	<u>\$4,357,102</u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

STATEMENT OF FUNCTIONAL EXPENSES
FOR THE YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 1988

(With Comparative Totals for 1987)

	Research	Access	Bibliography	Librarianship	Preservation Commission	Total Program	Administration	Year ended June 30	
								1988	1987
Unrestricted									
Grants and contracts	\$ 22,983	\$ 40,325		\$ 67,275		\$ 130,583		\$ 130,583	\$ 40,646
Refunds and overappropriations		(2,439)	\$ (192)	(27,977)		(30,608)		(30,608)	(9,140)
Staff and travel		24,775	51,888	31,504	\$ 4,671	112,838	\$128,797	241,635	213,686
Advisory committees and consultants		3,464	34,469	10,297	1,354	49,584		49,584	56,932
Board expenses							23,528	23,528	22,548
Office expenses			98	2,071	1,922	4,091	8,636	12,727	12,303
Support services			55,419	18,473	81,299	155,191	73,892	229,083	258,419
	<u>22,983</u>	<u>66,125</u>	<u>141,682</u>	<u>101,643</u>	<u>89,246</u>	<u>421,679</u>	<u>234,853</u>	<u>656,532</u>	<u>595,394</u>
Restricted									
Grants and contracts	92,125	94,970			74,131	261,226		261,226	562,347
Refunds and overappropriations		(29,622)	(591)	(6,897)		(37,110)		(37,110)	(131,443)
Staff and travel	132,153	29,030		14,846	195,091	371,120		371,120	188,086
Advisory committees and consultants	15,319	39,860	591	2,753	15,875	74,398		74,398	67,421
Office expenses	1,366	1,916		120	30,885	34,287		34,287	8,820
Support services	92,366	18,473		18,473	11,067	140,379		140,379	116,766
	<u>333,329</u>	<u>154,627</u>		<u>29,295</u>	<u>327,049</u>	<u>844,300</u>		<u>844,300</u>	<u>811,997</u>
Total expenses	<u>\$356,312</u>	<u>\$220,752</u>	<u>\$141,682</u>	<u>\$130,938</u>	<u>\$416,295</u>	<u>\$1,265,979</u>	<u>\$234,853</u>	<u>\$1,500,832</u>	<u>\$1,407,391</u>

Notes to Financial Statements

JUNE 30, 1988 AND 1987

Note 1—Organization

The Council on Library Resources, Inc. (Council) is a non-profit organization incorporated under the laws of the District of Columbia in 1956 for the purpose of promoting library research. The Council's operations are financed through unrestricted general support grants and through several restricted grants from private foundations and other sources. The Council conducts its work through directly administered projects as well as grants to and contracts with other organizations or individuals.

The Council, an exempt operating foundation, is exempt from Federal income tax under Internal Revenue Code section 501(c)(3).

Note 2—Summary of Significant Accounting Policies

The Council's financial statements have been prepared on the accrual basis of accounting. The significant accounting policies followed in the preparation of the financial statements are described below.

Grants

Grants are recorded as receivables and deferred revenue when the Council is notified that it has been awarded the funds. Unrestricted grant revenue is recognized in the income statement in accordance with the budgeted annual payments specified by the grantors. Restricted grant revenue is recognized when the related expenses are incurred.

Grant and contract expenses are recorded when the recipients are notified that they are to receive the funds. Current period expenses are reduced for grant refunds and overappropriations.

Contributions

Various universities have made restricted contributions to support the Commission on Preservation and Access. Voluntary contributions to fund this program are recorded as deferred revenue when received. Contribution revenue is recognized when the related expenses are incurred (see Note 5).

Investments and investment income

Short-term investments, which primarily consist of treasury bills and deposits in a money market fund, are recorded at cost which approximates market. Investment income is not restricted by the related grants and accordingly is recognized as unrestricted revenue.

Functional allocation of expenses

Costs of providing the various programs of the Council have been summarized on a functional basis in the accompanying financial statements. Certain indirect costs

identified as support services costs have been allocated to programs and administration on a systematic basis. These costs primarily include salary, benefits, rent and other expenses.

Furniture and equipment

The costs of office furniture and equipment are consistently charged to expense when incurred. The Council does not consider such expenditures to be material to warrant capitalization and depreciation.

Note 3—Retirement Plan

Employees are eligible for participation in the Council's defined contribution retirement annuity program administered through the TIAA/CREF insurance companies. Individual contracts issued under the plan provide for full and immediate vesting of both the Council's and employees' contributions. The Council's contribution was approximately \$84,000 and \$59,000 for fiscal years 1988 and 1987, respectively.

Note 4—Commitments

The Council entered into a lease agreement for office space expiring in 1990. The minimum future rentals will be approximately \$140,000 for each of the two remaining years. As part of this lease agreement, the Council will continue to be assessed an annual charge based on its proportionate share of the increase in the operating costs of the building. For the years ended June 30, 1988 and 1987, rent expense totaled \$133,000 and \$124,000, respectively, of which approximately \$21,000 and \$17,000, respectively, represents the Council's share of the increase in the operating costs.

The Council subleases a portion of its leased office space. Rental income from this sublease amounted to approximately \$35,000 and \$32,000 in fiscal years 1988 and 1987, respectively, and was used to offset office rent expense.

Note 5—Events Subsequent to June 30, 1988

Through June 30, 1988, the Commission on Preservation and Access was a Council program. On July 1, 1988, the Commission was incorporated as a separate nonprofit entity in the District of Columbia. Application for tax exemption under section 501(c)(3) of the Internal Revenue code is pending.

The Council will transfer to the Commission the \$1,952,000 balance of grants and contributions at June 30, 1988 designated as support for the Commission. The Commission has agreed to reimburse the Council for all direct and indirect costs incurred in providing office space and employee and administrative services to the Commission.

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